

How Bureaucratic Time-Tactics Can Shape Politics

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Summary

- We study how bureaucratic procedures and institutional rules are used by public bureaucrats to influence the speed of public policy development via a survey among 1,670 national public bureaucrats in Norway.
 - The temporal dimensions of bureaucratic procedures are shown to be a carefully considered part of policy-making processes.
 - Building on a survey experiment, we show that proximity to elections makes bureaucrats less – *not* more – inclined to slow down the policy-making process.
 - Bureaucrats are less likely to fast-track policies with negative expert assessments.
 - Both findings are stronger among bureaucrats that are politically aligned with the government in power, revealing how politics impacts upon bureaucratic procedures.
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1. Introduction

Politicians commonly delegate much of the nuts and bolts of policy formulation, development and implementation to public administrations. Academic scholarship has intensively investigated the nature and determinants of this delegation process, as well as how it allows public administrators to influence the policy-making process. Recent public debates on the ‘democratic deficit’ of public administrations and the administrative ‘deep state’, however, have renewed long-standing concerns about this policy influence of unelected bureaucrats.

Much of this discussion has focused on how public administrations affect the **content** of public policies. Recent research by Vibeke Kroken, Zuzana Murdoch and Benny Geys instead studies when and how public administrations may exploit their control over bureaucratic procedures and institutional rules to influence the **speed** – or lack thereof – of the policy-making process. Clearly, rigid requirements, complex rules, and/or inefficient workflows tend to cause delays, but such administrative frictions need not always arise. That is, public administrations often have at least some leeway about whether to introduce and/or maintain administrative roadblocks rather than cutting through the red tape. Hence, a key question is: *Under which conditions do public administrations exploit administrative procedures and rules to slow down – or speed up – policy-making processes?*

2. Survey design

We tackle this question via a survey questionnaire fielded in November-December 2023 among approximately 4,000 Norwegian national-level public bureaucrats, and obtained 1,670 usable responses. The key

question of interest asks respondents to imagine that *“The minister responsible for your policy area wants to introduce an ambitious policy measure, which will require significant changes to existing legislation. Your unit holds the primary responsibility to prepare this new policy initiative. In your opinion, how likely is it that the civil service will adopt the following procedures in this situation?”*

We provide respondents with eight answer options – in random order – that capture a range of procedural actions that can either slow down (statements 1-4) or speed up (statements 5-8) the policy-making process. These procedures are formulated in line with the official requirements and regulations imposed on Norway’s national public administration (Utredningsinstruksen 2016), and were checked for their realism and validity by current and former top civil servants. Answers were recorded on a five-point scale: 1 ‘not likely at all’, 2 ‘unlikely’, 3 ‘somewhat likely’, 4 ‘likely’, 5 ‘very likely’.

1. Propose the longest possible response deadlines for public consultation and input from other relevant ministries (e.g. more than 3 months).
2. Propose cost-benefit analyses, even if they are strictly speaking not required.
3. Spend more time than necessary identifying, investigating and assessing alternative measures.
4. Investigate legal arguments against rapid implementation of the proposed measures.
5. Propose the shortest possible response deadlines for public consultation and input from other relevant ministries (e.g. less than 6 weeks).
6. Argue for omitting cost-benefit analyses.
7. Do not spend more time than absolutely necessary on identifying, investigating and assessing alternative measures.

- Investigate legal arguments in support of rapid implementation of the proposed measures.

A key aspect of our survey design is that we randomly vary some of the details in the information provided to our respondents (i.e. a between-subject survey experiment). This allows us to evaluate how changes in the decision-making context might affect public bureaucrats' reliance on specific bureaucratic procedures. We thereby focus on the role of an upcoming election (suggested to take place in 'about nine months'), as well as expert assessments of the proposed policies (suggested to be either 'positive' or 'negative'). The underlying theoretical argument is that upcoming elections directly affect the time-frame available to public bureaucrats, while expert assessments of a policy under development may influence bureaucrats' perceptions about the viability and/or desirability of a policy proposal.

3. Main findings

Our main results are illustrated in Figure 1, which shows the mean response across all respondents for each of the eight procedural actions (i.e. independent of our experimental treatments). Given the answer scale employed in the survey, average values around 2 imply that the action is rather unlikely to cross bureaucrats' minds during a policy-making process, while values above 3 make the action at least somewhat likely. With that in mind, a first observation from Figure 1 is that, on average, actions that speed up a policy-making process are more likely to be considered than actions that slow down the process. While this may initially appear surprising given debates about red tape and bureaucratic frictions, it is consistent with the notion that bureaucrats must serve the government of the day to the best of their ability – and often consider this to be one of

their primary tasks. Hence, our findings suggest that public bureaucrats are on the whole at least willing to find ways within the bureaucratic procedures and institutional rules to make politicians' wishes a reality as soon as possible.

A second, though related, observation from Figure 1 is that certain types of procedures appear to offer more leeway than others. For instance, the amount of time used to identify, investigate and assess alternative measures appears to provide most leeway when speeding up decision-making processes (i.e. there is a large difference between the 3rd and 7th bar in Figure 1). The reverse is true for cost-benefit and risk assessments, which appear to be perceived as a requirement that is particularly hard to circumvent (i.e. the 2nd bar in Figure 1 is higher than the equivalent 6th bar). Finally, developing legal arguments is central to any policy-making process, and thus is unsurprisingly among the most likely bureaucratic actions when slowing down *and* speeding up the process.

Not shown in Figure 1 is what happens when we split the analysis by our two experimental conditions (i.e. upcoming elections, and expert assessments). Here, our central findings reveal that approaching elections do *not* increase the likelihood of using delaying tactics, but, instead, create time pressures to 'get things done' before a potential shift in the political balance of power. In practice, this means that the bars on the right-hand side of Figure 1 tend to get higher relative to those on the left-hand side of Figure 1 when an approaching election is mentioned to our respondents. Interestingly, this is particularly true among public administrators whose political leaning matches that of the current government. One potential explanation is that bureaucrats supporting the government may be particularly keen to help the government

achieve (some of) its aims prior to a potential political turnover.

Finally, we find that respondents show an increased preference to slow down administrative processes when faced with policies assessed to have important shortcomings. In other words, the bars on the left-hand side of Figure 1 tend to get higher when respondents are told that experts have expressed doubts about the policy under evaluation. These results are reminiscent of recent evidence showing that bureaucrats are willing to engage in ‘shirk and sabotage’ in response to democratic backsliding and policies perceived to restrict democratic rights (Schuster et al. 2022; Yesilkagit et al. 2024; Silveira et al. 2026). Interestingly, however, bureaucrats are *not* willing fast-track policies with desirable characteristics, which suggests that they are keen to at least provide a minimal level of quality assurance.

4. Policy recommendations

Although our findings naturally relate to one country with a particular set of institutional characteristics, our analysis nonetheless may offer important insights for policy makers.

First, our findings show that bureaucrats display differences in their willingness to engage in certain actions that speed up – or slow down – policy-making processes. This provides important lessons for politicians who may be keen to push for faster responses from the bureaucracy. Specifically, **asking the bureaucracy to explore only few alternative measures and focus on the development of supportive legal arguments is more likely to be met with a positive response than pushing the bureaucracy to forego cost-benefit and risk assessments.**

Second, our results call for **additional ethical training of public bureaucrats as part of their on-boarding procedures.** Given that our respondents are willing to use bureaucratic procedures and institutional rules that affect the speed of policy-making processes, it is important to make them aware of the dos and don’ts of such bureaucratic ‘time tactics’. Clear ethical guidelines and procedures should also be included in staff codes of conduct – much the same as the explicit guidelines and procedures that already exist regarding, for instance, the disclosure of confidential information.

Third, our results call for **increasing societal awareness about the temporal aspects of bureaucratic practices.** Most procedures included in our analysis were originally developed to help safeguard the integrity of public policy, and public bureaucrats often think of their use in terms of that overarching goal. Providing clarity about the motivations and foundations of bureaucratic actions would help address perceived accountability concerns, and thereby the level of trust in and legitimacy of public administrations.

Finally, we are living in a time where social and political pressures often force bureaucrats to increasingly balance pressing demands for swift action with a critical need for careful evaluation and preparation. Politicians and governments across the globe have furthermore shown an increasing appetite to test established legal boundaries. While our analysis suggests that this may increase the likelihood of slow-rolling procedural actions within the bureaucracy, it puts added **pressure on public administrations to reconcile their role in serving the government of the day with their role in ensuring the integrity of public policy.**

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

Figures:

Figure 1. Use of procedural actions that slow down or speed up policy-making processes

Notes: The figure studies the mean value of respondents' answers to the question "How likely is it that the civil service will adopt the following procedures in this situation?" (answers are coded from 1 'not likely at all' to 5 'very likely'). Each bar shows the response for one time tactic (see main text for detailed description), where answer options to the left (right) of the vertical black line reflect tactics that slow down (speed up) the policy-making process. These procedural actions are based on examples reported in extant academic research, as well as the official requirements and regulations imposed on Norway's national public administration (Utredningsinstruksen 2016).

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Further Information:

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